

LITERACY AND ADULT EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of adult literacy in Uzbekistan, the analysis of the state of this issue, literacy among men and women. The potential of adult learning and education in solving employment problems with the aim of increasing competitiveness in all spheres of life: economic, political, cultural, as well as their family members.*

Keywords: *competitiveness, potential, employment problems, reform paths, knowledge and skills, literacy rate, educational structures, current state and development prospects.*

The development of the Adult Education system and lifelong learning have recently become the subject of wide discussion by all interested parties, including the state, educational structures, civil society institutions, and, of course, adults themselves. Adult education in Uzbekistan, as well as for any other country in the world that has embarked on the path of reforms for the development and prosperity of its inhabitants, is of great importance at the present stage. A special moment is literacy and adult education. Adults with low levels of literacy and education naturally become uncompetitive in all spheres of life: economic, political, cultural, and with them their family members [1].

Lack of knowledge and skills is felt by about 60% of the adult population in Uzbekistan. This is not surprising, since access to higher education for the population has been extremely limited for many years. The development of adult education would fill this gap by making the workforce more skilled. Senator Diloram Tashmukhamedova writes about the new edition of the law "On Education" and how adult education should develop: on average, the more prosperous the country, the higher the level of participation [2].

Unfortunately, in Uzbekistan, the potential of adult learning and education in solving employment problems is practically not used. The existing educational institutions do not cover the needs of the adult population, especially the unemployed, in acquiring new knowledge and skills.

In Uzbekistan, the level of adult participation in education and training is very low compared to other countries. These are the results of a survey on the project which conducted in 2019 "Adult learning and education in Uzbekistan: current state and development prospects".

A study on the project "Training and education of adults in Uzbekistan: current state and development prospects" revealed a high need for adults in training. Lack of knowledge and skills is felt by more than 70% of young people aged 24-33 years old, respondents in the age group of 34-42 years old agree with them. In total, the share of respondents who indicated that they lack knowledge and skills is 60%. Almost half of the respondents pointed to the lack of opportunities, citing the lack of time due to family circumstances, the high cost of training, and the employer's lack of interest as reasons.

Uzbekistan will be able to reach the forefront only through education, and what is important - by connecting all segments of the population to it. However, for a long time the legislative framework in the field of education was imperfect. On August 7, 2020, the Senate approved the

Education Law, which for the first time defines various forms of education, which will serve as the basis for a significant expansion of educational services

These include “family education and self-education”, “inclusive education”, “adult learning and education” (ED). The latter term includes formal, non-formal and informal learning, through which adults expand their knowledge throughout their lives, enrich their skills and abilities, and acquire a profession in demand. Earlier I wrote about the importance of developing the field of adult learning and education, this issue is of vital importance today.

Our country needs educated youth and a strong economy. A new culture of learning is emerging around the world to meet the demands of the economy of the future. Our country needs educated youth and a strong economy.

A new culture of learning is emerging around the world to meet the demands of the economy of the future. The overall goal of the economy and the education system is to train competitive and responsible personnel capable of making decisions independently, motivated for self-development and retraining throughout life.[5] Annual surveys can help determine the extent to which adults participate in ALE. This will make it possible to monitor progress in this area and develop / adjust existing strategies for the development of adult learning and education and other state programs for the socio-economic development of the country.

Generally, higher income countries have higher participation rates in adult learning and education. These countries are members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development and have the highest levels of employment and productivity

The results of the study by scientists showed a low level of adult participation in education and training. Moreover, the older the person, the less he shows interest in this issue. Women's participation rates in formal and non-formal education slightly exceed those of men. At the same time, the latter have shown great activity in informal learning.[6]

Nearly half of those surveyed noted a lack of training opportunities. The reasons cited were lack of time due to family circumstances, high tuition fees, and lack of employer's permission. Low income levels with an average household size of 5.8 people with a high dependency burden due to non-working family members and high tuition costs can together be a serious barrier to adult participation in learning and education.

Residents of cities are more active in learning. However, the rural population showed a great need for additional skills and knowledge. The presence of regional differences may indicate a lack of equal opportunities in adults' access to education and training. These countries are members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development and have the highest levels of employment and productivity

Despite the presence of an extensive network of formal education institutions, their role in improving the participation of the adult population in education remains extremely low. The same conclusion applies to non-formal education, where the share of formal education institutions is only 10%.

The main challenge for adult learning and education around the world is to reach those who need it most. This is the main message of the fifth Global Report on Adult Learning and Education (GRALE 5), which will be published on 15 June 2022 during the seventh report of UNESCO, shows that despite the progress made, especially with regard to women's participation, those who are more The most needy for adult education are disadvantaged and vulnerable groups, such as students from the indigenous population, rural population, migrants, senior citizens, people with disabilities [7].

It is necessary to develop a concept for the development of adult learning and education for the period up to 2030, aimed at solving the complex problems associated with increasing adult participation in learning.

About 60% of countries reported no improvement in the participation of people with disabilities, migrants and prisoners. 24% of countries reported a decline in rural participation. The participation of older people also fell in 24% of the 159 countries surveyed. GRALE 5 calls for a major transformation in Member States' approach to adult learning and education, backed by adequate investment, so that everyone can enjoy the benefits of adult learning and education.

“I urge governments and the international community to join forces and take action to ensure that the right to education is realized for all, regardless of age, identity or place of residence,” said UNESCO Director-General Audrey Azoulay.

“Rapid technological and social transformations, as well as massive global challenges, require citizens to have access to new knowledge throughout their lives. Retraining and upgrading through adult learning and education should become routine. The main skill of the 21st century is the ability to learn” [13].

More than half of the countries have reported an increase in participation in adult learning and education since 2018, but challenges remain. Although the participation of women and youth has increased significantly, overall participation in adult learning and education is still insufficient. These data testify to the insufficient use of the potential of state educational institutions for the development of formal and non-formal education in the country.

In 23% of the 159 countries that provided data for GRALE 5, less than 1% of youth and adults aged 15 and over participate in education and training programs. Sub-Saharan Africa leads by a wide margin, with 59% of countries reporting that at least one in five adults benefit from education. This rate drops to just 16% in Latin America and the Caribbean and to 25% in Europe.

The high participation rate in Africa can be partly explained by the high demand for adult literacy and second chances for education. Most countries reported progress in terms of curriculum quality, assessment and professional development of adult educators. More than two-thirds of them reported progress in pre-service and in-service training for ALE teachers, as well as in employment. Although this progress differs significantly by region and income group, it contributes to improving the quality of adult education

Responding to modern challenges such as climate change and digitalization requires citizens to be informed, educated and active so that they recognize both their shared humanity and their obligations to other species and to the planet. Citizenship education is a key tool in this effort.

GRALE Special Thematic Chapter 5 shows that nearly three-quarters (74%) of countries are developing or implementing citizenship education policies.

Published by the UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning, the Global Report on Adult Learning and Education tracks the extent to which UNESCO Member States are implementing their international commitments to adult learning and education in practice. The reports combine survey data, policy analysis and case studies to provide policy makers and practitioners with sound advice and good practice examples from the International Conference on Adult Education in Marrakech, Morocco.

In the course of the study, it was found that the employed are more likely to receive training compared to the unemployed. Training is received mainly by specialists who already have higher education. Respondents with secondary vocational education rarely study after the age of 25. The exceptions are paramedical and some other workers who are required to regularly take refresher courses. The main reason why respondents study is the desire to maintain or improve their positions at work. By the way, this worries men more than women.

The most demanded areas of study are medicine, pedagogy and other humanitarian disciplines. The demand for such training is mainly supported by women. Among men, economic and engineering specialties are most in demand; There are very few people who want to get an education in the field of information technology.

Uzbek arts and crafts have long been well-deserved fame. The historical conditions in which the culture of the Uzbek people developed predetermined a special role for applied art. For many centuries created by the people: its technical and artistic traditions. Applied art is every day, its main feature is a deep connection between artistic creativity and material needs. The organic fusion of the artistic and the practically necessary creates an inseparable unity of ideological-artistic and social-practical functions. A work of applied art is distinguished by the expediency of forms, the unity of form and design. The social nature of decorative art is its collectivity, art is the legacy of many generations, it is a series of successive layers, the most ancient of which reflect the original culture of the people deeply imprinted in its art. The works of all genres of this art are determined by the diversity of artistic traditions introduced by the peoples that made up the Uzbek nation [19].

The creations of Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and other masters were famous far beyond the borders of their homeland and have not lost their relevance since then. Suzani embroideries, skullcaps, knives, carpets, ceramics, silk and embossing - handmade by local artisans make up the unique exotic of Uzbekistan.

Of course, a huge role in the preservation of traditions is the participation of adults in this process.

There are many dynasties in Uzbekistan. In all this, folk craftsmen take an active part, who from generation to generation pass on the traditions of making objects of folk arts and crafts and teach young people this: ceramics, wood carving, gold embroidery, suzani, patchwork, making abr fabrics and much more. The most demanded areas of study are medicine, pedagogy and other

humanitarian disciplines. The demand for such training is mainly supported by women. Among men, economic and engineering specialties are most in demand; There are very few people who want to get an education in the field of information technology.

At the conference “Adult Learning and Education in Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals”, held last year in Weimar, representatives of UNESCO, the International Council for Adult Education, the European Association for Adult Education noted good examples from the practice of adult education in Belarus, the Balkan countries, and countries of Southeast Asia and Latin America.

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